

Studies on Dyes derived from Cinnoline

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In our present study several cyanines and merocyanines have been synthesised from 4-methyl cinnoline. Utilising their absorption data, certain generalisations on the influence of structural changes on absorption and sensitisation have been made

Cyanine dyes from heterocyclic compounds containing one nitrogen atom in the ring such as quinaldine and lepidine etc. are well known^{1,2}. The present investigation has been directed to the preparation of dyes from heterocyclic ring systems containing more than one nitrogen atoms.

4-Methyl cinnoline was prepared from methyl anthranilate by Grignard's reaction followed by the cyclisation of diazotised amine^{3,4}. It was quaternised by heating on a water bath with methyl iodide in a sealed tube for 4 hours. The unsymmetrical monomethine cyanines (I, n = 0) were prepared by refluxing these quaternary salts with methyl mercapto quaternary salts of benzothiazole and 4-phenyl thiazole in acetic anhydride. The unsymmetrical tri- and penta-methine cyanines (I, n = 1 and 2 respectively) were prepared by condensing the 2-(2'-acetanilido vinyl) and 2-(4'-acetanilido-1,3-butadienyl) derivatives of other 2-methyl quaternary salts with 4-methyl cinnoline methiodides in acetic anhydride and triethylamine

(I)

Variable basic nuclei

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The merocyanines (II, $n = 1$ and 2) were prepared by the condensation of the quaternary salts of 4-methyl cinnoline with ethoxy methylene or ethoxy allylidene derivatives of ketomethylene compounds in acetic anhydride and triethylamine.

Variable acidic nuclei

The relative basicity of cinnoline nucleus as compared to benzothiazole and benzoxazole has been evaluated with the help of "deviation factor". As postulated by Brooker⁵ in a series of merocyanines containing the same acidic nucleus and variable basic nuclei the deviation is maximum for the least basic nucleus and as the basicity is increased, the deviation is correspondingly decreased. Deviation is considered as the difference between the absorption maximum of the corresponding symmetrical cyanine and the oxonol. The deviation is calculated as illustrated here by taking the case of merocyanine derived from 4-methyl cinnoline and acidic nucleus pyrazolone. The absorption maximum of the symmetrical cyanine derived from cinnoline is $680\text{ m}\mu$ and that of the oxonol derived from pyrazolone is $438\text{ m}\mu$. The merocyanine constituted from cinnoline and pyrazolone, however, absorbs at $594\text{ m}\mu$. Deviation is, therefore $-35\text{ m}\mu$. As already reported⁶, the deviations of merocyanines derived from the acidic nucleus pyrazolone and the basic nuclei benzothiazole and benzoxazole are $11.5\text{ m}\mu$ and $42\text{ m}\mu$ respectively. The least deviation in case of cinnoline nucleus shows that cinnoline is more basic than benzothiazole which in turn is more basic than benzoxazole.

The sensitisation spectra shows that both cyanines and merocyanines derived from cinnoline are desensitisers

EXPERIMENTAL

4-Methyl cinnoline methiodide: 4-Methyl cinnoline (1.44 gm.) and methyl iodide (1.42 gm.) were heated in a sealed tube on a water bath for 2 hours. The solid obtained was washed with ether and crystallised from minimum amount of ethanol. Yield—82%, M.P. 205° . (Found : N, 9.62; I, 44.2; $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{11}\text{N}_2\text{I}$ requires N, 9.79; I, 44.32%).

(3-Methyl 4-phenyl thiazole) (4-methyl cinnoline) 2-2'-methin cyanine iodide: 4-Methyl cinnoline methiodide (0.15 gm.) and 2-methyl mercapto 4-phenyl thiazole methiodide (0.17 gm.) were refluxed in acetic anhydride (5 cc) and triethylamine (2 drops) for half an hour.

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The product separated on cooling and was crystallised from alcohol. Yield—65%, M.P. 270°. (Found : C, 52.31; H, 3.62; $C_{20}H_{18}N_3SI$ requires C, 52.40; H, 3.71%).

The dye absorbs at 500 $m\mu$ in ethanol.

(3-Methyl benzothiazole) (4-methyl cinnoline) 2-2'-methin cyanine iodide : 4-Methyl cinnoline methiodide (0.15 gm.) and 2-methyl mercapto benzothiazole methiodide (0.16 gm.) were refluxed with acetic anhydride (5 cc.) and triethylamine (2 drops) and the dye was isolated as before. Yield—60%, M.P.—265°. (Found : C, 49.78; H 3.62; $C_{18}H_{16}N_3SI$ requires C, 49.89; H, 3.69%).

The dye shows absorption maximum at 530 $m\mu$ in ethanol.

(3-Methyl benzothiazole) (4-methyl cinnoline) 2-2'-trimethin cyanine iodide : 4-Methyl cinnoline methiodide (0.5 gm.) and 2-(2'-acetanilidovinyl) 3-methyl benzothiazolium iodide (0.63 gm.) were warmed gently with acetic anhydride (5 ml.) and triethylamine (2 drops). It was chilled and the solid which separated was crystallised from ethanol

The m.p., absorption data of the related trimethin cyanines derived from different heterocyclic compounds are given in the Table I.

TABLE I

Unsymmetrical trimethin cyanine derived from cinnoline

Nature of the nucleus 'B'	Yield %	M.P. °C	λ max in $m\mu$	% Carbon		% Hydrogen	
				Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.
Benzothiazole	65	220	630	52.18	52.29	3.87	3.92
4-Phenyl thiazole	60	260	625	54.38	54.44	4.08	4.12
Quinaldine	59	235	650	58.23	58.28	4.37	4.41
Lepidine	50	230	670	58.19	58.28	4.33	4.41
alpha-Naphthathiazole	50	260	642	56.49	56.58	3.85	3.92
beta-Naphthathiazole	52	205	642	56.53	56.58	3.87	3.92
Benzoxazole	60	250	595	54.12	54.18	4.03	4.06
beta-Naphthoxazole	60	260	620	58.31	58.42	4.03	4.05

(3-Methyl benzothiazole) (4-methyl cinnoline) 2-2'-pentamethin cyanine iodide : A mixture of 4-methyl cinnoline methiodide (0.17 gm) and 2-(4'-acetanilido butadienyl-3-methyl) benzothiazolium iodide was refluxed with acetic anhydride (5 ml.) and triethylamine (2 drops)

for 1 hour. The bronzy green solid separated after cooling and was crystallised from methanol. Yield—52%, M.P. 243°. (Found : C, 54.39; H, 4.06; $C_{23}H_{21}N_3SI$ requires C, 54.44; H, 4.12%).

The dye shows absorption maxima at 670 $m\mu$ in ethanol.

Bis (1-methyl cinnoline) 2-2'-trimethin cyanine iodide : 4-Methyl cinnoline methiodide (1.5 gm.) and diphenyl formamidine (1.9 gm.) were warmed with acetic anhydride (10 ml.) and triethylamine. The product was isolated on cooling in the form of green needles. Yield—60%, M.P. 130°.

The dye absorbs at 680 $m\mu$ in ethanol.

Preparation of merocyanines : 4-Methyl cinnoline methiodide (0.1 mole) and ethoxy methylene (for $n = 1$) or ethoxy allylidene (for $n = 2$) intermediates of ketomethylene compound (0.1 M) were refluxed with acetic anhydride (5 cc.) and triethylamine (2 drops) for 30 minutes. It was cooled and the solid obtained on addition of water was crystallised from alcohol.

The m.p. and analytical data of various merocyanines prepared are recorded in the Table II

TABLE II

Merocyanines derived from cinnoline

Nature of the nucleus 'A'	Value of 'n'	Yield %	M.P. °C	λ_{max} in $m\mu$	% Carbon		% Hydrogen	
					Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.
Pyrazolone	1	52	234	594	66.63	66.67	4.72	4.76
Thiobarbituric acid	1	60	245	580	69.02	69.04	4.38	4.42
<i>p</i> -Chloro phenyl oxazolone	1	65	230	650	66.01	66.03	3.82	3.85
<i>p</i> -Tolyl oxazolone	1	65	198	640	73.39	73.47	4.89	4.95
Phenyl oxazolone	1	65	225	640	72.88	72.95	4.47	4.55
Isocoumaranone	1	60	220	610	74.42	74.49	4.76	4.82
-do-	2	50	225	660	76.80	76.83	4.79	4.87
Thiobarbituric acid	2	45	251	645	71.02	71.06	4.39	4.48

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